

INSILICO
WORLD

Solution Dossier

Detailed collection of the results produced within the In Silico World project

Introduction

Welcome to the In Silico World project dossier, a comprehensive record of the groundbreaking solutions developed to advance healthcare through computational models and simulations. The In Silico World project aims at accelerating the uptake of modelling and simulation technologies used for the development and regulatory assessment of medicines and medical devices, by lowering seven identified barriers: development, validation, accreditation, optimisation, exploitation, information, and training.

This dossier details our achievements in enhancing the accuracy, efficiency, and safety of different medical products.

AngioSupport

AngioSupport is a 1D/0D model to predict pressure and flow waves in the coronary arteries based on standard bi-plane angiographic data although CT-data can also be used. A sophisticated numerical implementation based on low-order (finite element-like) interpolation functions is used to integrate the 1D model with the 0D components.

In In Silico World (ISW), AngioSupport will be used to perform an in-silico version of the FAME 1 study in which decision-making based on classical eye-balling of the angiograms is compared with measured FFR-based methods (Tonino et. Al, 2009).

For this, the FFRValid data collection will be used. Based on this also concepts of using collections of synthetic datasets will be evaluated. In addition, AngioSupport will be used as a clinical decision-making tool for clinicians to decide whether and what treatment results in the best outcome for the patient.

BoneStrength

BoneStrength is an In Silico Trial solution to assess the efficacy of pharmacological treatments for osteoporosis and prevention of fragility fractures. At the core of BoneStrength, there is BBCT (Bologna Biomechanical Computed Tomography), a Digital Twin pipeline to estimate patient-specific hip fracture risk, based on a CT scan of the femur and patient-specific height and weight.

The aim of BoneStrength is to simulate phase III clinical trials by using a large number of virtual patients (~1000). For each patient, bone ageing with and without pharmacological treatments is simulated over several years, in order to predict hip fracture incidence in the different scenarios.

For this solution, a Qualification Advice with EMA has been pursued.

ForceLoss

Model as falsification tool for the differential diagnosis of dynapenia

The loss of muscle force, also known as dynapenia, has multiple causes. It could be that your muscles became weaker as they lost mass (sarcopenia), or they cannot be activated efficiently (deficit in neuromuscular control) or because the link between brain and muscles, both working fine per se, is broken (innervation problem).

Each of the above would require a different and specific treatment.

The ForceLoss project aims to enable the identification of the originating cause (differential diagnosis) of dynapenia, leveraging on the use of computer models of the human musculoskeletal system to support clinical decision making.

Such models, built off a person's own data (e.g., medical imaging data), will be employed to simulate a maximal contraction during knee extension.

Different scenarios (e.g., real vs optimal) will be tested and the simulation results will be compared to real data collected on the same person in the lab and data from a healthy population.

The ForceLoss solution may be of further use in the design of clinical trials for drugs aiming to prevent sarcopenia, where the enrollment of patients with dynapenia not due to sarcopenia could be detrimental.

InSole

InSole aims to combine subject-specific musculoskeletal models with novel predictive simulations for the personalized prescription of 3D printed corrective shoe insoles.

The integrated framework utilizes experimental measurements from a dedicated movement analysis dataset and plantar pressure to predict the optimal corrective stiffness and geometry of a custom 3D printed insoles to correct dynamic foot deformities during locomotion. The framework has been developed and validated in a healthy population and will be extended to a larger patient group and other dynamic foot pathologies.

The framework consists of the following steps:

- Patient complaint/presentation
- Patient assessment (i.e., anatomy, movement pattern, and plantar pressure)
- Personalised computational model development
- Simulation of movement using measured data
- Insole optimization simulations (stiffness and geometry)
- Prescription of optimized insoles

In the In Silico World project, KU Leuven will develop and validate it as a solution to evaluate and design patient-specific insoles for numerous deformities.

KU Leuven will provide the methodological development and validation, whereas Materialise Motion will be responsible for insole framework deployment as an online service, integration with the industrial manufacturing process and associated legal and regulatory issues.

NeoIntima3D

Thrombosis

Platelet-clot formation

ISR3D is a specific example of a model for neointima (new tissue) formation in the cardiovascular system, which plays an especially large role in recovery after medical intravascular intervention, e.g. in healing and scar formation. NeoIntima3D uses a more general model to provide a solution that predicts the risk of late thrombosis in vascular stenting.

Late thrombosis is a particularly dangerous condition. The thrombus that forms on a thrombogenic surface, such as an arterial ulcer or exposed metal struts of a stent, may break off and completely cut off the blood flow in the artery. The exact reasons and mechanisms of late thrombosis are still ill-understood. It is a rather infrequent event, e.g. late stent thrombosis happens in less than 1% of cases, but if it occurs, it leads to myocardial infarction and death in up to 80% of cases.

What is currently missing are models that are capable to predict such long-term effects as of late thrombosis. Validation will then be along two lines, one to predict if and where a thrombosis may occur, and one to predict when a thrombus could form. The first line will depend on microfluidics data, the second on clinical data.

OcDefects

OcDefects is a mechanobiology model of the osteochondral cartilage regeneration process, to be used for In Silico trials of an Advanced Therapeutic Medicinal Product (ATMP) for the repair of deep osteochondral defects. Here, the focus will be on knee defects, but the approach is generic and could be used to develop models to test other ATMPs.

Starting from gait data, the mechanical requirements of the ATMP are derived. An atlas of the OA process, built at ULG from single-cell RNA Seq data available in the literature, will be used to identify potential drug targets in a systems biology approach using a regulatory network inferred from the transcriptomics data (prototype available).

In order to capture the behaviour of the ATMP in its clinical setting, the mechanical model will be coupled to the in-house developed cell growth model as well as the intracellular model through the mechanobiology-related pathways. Existing OA collections will be used to an in silico OA population.

UISS-COVID19

Systemic Disorders

Fever, Fatigue, Dry Cough, Headache, Hypoxemia, Lymphopenia, Acute Cardiac Injury

Respiratory Disorders

Sneezing, Rnaemia, Rhinorrhea, Sore Throat, Ground Glass Opacities, Respiratory Distress Syndrome

The Universal Immune System Simulator – COVID19 (UISS-COVID19) predicts the dynamics of SARS-CoV-2 immune system competition within the host. COVID19 is a severe respiratory infection that affects humans and its outburst recently became a pandemic emergency.

To promptly and rapidly respond to these dramatic pandemic events, the application of in silico trials can be used for designing and testing medicines against SARS-CoV-2 and speedup the vaccine discovery pipeline, predicting any therapeutic failure and minimizing undesired effects.

UISS-COVID19 consists in an in silico platform that showed to be in very good agreement with the latest literature outcome in predicting SARS-CoV-2 dynamics and related immune system host response, including cytokines involvement.

Moreover, it has been used to predict the outcome of several approaches to design an effective vaccines and therapies. UISS-COVID19 is ready to be used as an in silico trial platform to predict the outcome of vaccination strategy against SARS-CoV-2.

The In Silico World planned work is to validate this code with a medium-size cohort of clinical cases collected from specific literature clinical studies.

UISS-MC

Physiological part

Simulation Part

The Universal Immune System Simulator – Mammary Carcinoma (UISS-MC) is an agent-based model specifically tailored to simulate the effects of tumor-preventive cell vaccines in HER-2/neu transgenic mice prone to the development of mammary carcinoma.

This solution combines a genetic algorithm engine to optimize dosage for vaccination schedules, suggesting effective cancer-preventive vaccination protocols competitive with human-designed protocols. Università degli Studi di Catania (UNICT) will use anonymized data coming from the Istituto Europeo di Oncologia in order to extend UISS-MC for clinical usage, validating its general predictive accuracy of the patient-specific modelling pipeline.

With the retrospective collections of experimental data, it will be possible to test the prediction accuracy of UISS-MC for immunotherapies against mammary carcinoma in humans.

UISS-MS

The Universal Immune System Simulator – Multiple Sclerosis (UISS-MS) predicts the outcome of specific treatments in patients affected by a relapsing-remitting form of multiple sclerosis.

It provides decision-support to MS specialist about the best treatment based on the disease characteristics and on the immunological profile of the patient. It can be also used to run in silico trials of new treatments.

For the validation of this solution, UNICT will use data collected at third party Multiple Sclerosis Center, Neurology Unit, Garibaldi Hospital, Catania, Italy.

Data involves at least 150 adults affected by the two most common form of multiple sclerosis, i.e. primary progressing relapsing-remitting MS and secondary progressing MS.

All data will be collected with after the written approval of hospital local ethics committee (Comitato Etico dell'Azienda Ospedaliera "Garibaldi"), followed by patients informed consent to participate to this study for research purposes.

UISS-TB

The Universal Immune System Simulator – Tuberculosis (UISS-TB) is a simulator of the immune system dynamics, particularly tailored to predict the response of the human immune system to the exposure to Mycobacterium tuberculosis.

It can be used as an in silico lab to predict the outcome of new vaccination strategies for active tuberculosis and it has already been validated with available data coming from clinical trials of two vaccines (RUTI and ID93+GLA-SE).

The consortium plans to complete its validation using anonymized data coming from patients enrolled in the STriTuVaD EC funded project, with a regulatory submission of qualification advice.

VirtualFD

VirtualFD is solution with a framework to simulate the virtual flow diverter (FD) deployment and the flow in and around intracranial aneurysms. The application takes into account the detailed mechanical properties and the hydrodynamic resistance of the FDs, both obtained from unique in-house measurements.

A measurement device has been recently developed to quantify the hydrodynamic resistance of the FDs, and this is an essential input information to the predictive model for perianeurismal flow simulations. The aim of the solution is to facilitate the in silico regulatory evaluation of flow diverters (FDs) used for the endovascular treatment of intracranial aneurysms.

The planned work for VirtualFD in ISW is to validate the solution with a medium-size cohort of clinical cases collected in a separate project at the National Institute of Mental Health, Neurology, and Neurosurgery (formerly: National Institute of Clinical Neurosciences).

The acquired results will aid the development of criteria to evaluate newly developed FDs, since at present the quality criteria for FDs are not properly defined. In addition to medical data, a database for mechanical properties and hydrodynamic resistances will be built using our in-house measurement systems.

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